

JAHON PEDAGOG MUTAXASISLARI FAOLIYATIDA “QOBILIYATI” VA
“PEDAGOGIK QOBILIYAT” TUSHUNCHALARINI MILLIY MENTALITET BILAN
BOG’LAGAN HOLDA TALABALAR PEDAGOGIK MAHORATINI OSHIRISH
VOSITALARI USTIDA ISHLASH.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada jahon pedagog mutaxasislari faoliyatida “qobiliyati” va “pedagogik qobiliyat” tushunchalarini milliy mentalitet bilan bog’lagan holda talabalar pedagogik mahoratini oshirish vositalari ustida ishlash ahamiyati ko’rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: xalqaro tashkilotlar, o’qitish texnologiyalari, ta’lim-tarbiya sifatini takomillashtirish, hamkorlik pedagogikasi, ta’limning kollaborativ va kooperativ texnologiyalari.

WORKING ON THE MEANS OF IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS
OF STUDENTS, LINKING THE CONCEPTS OF “ABILITY” AND “PEDAGOGICAL
ABILITY” WITH THE NATIONAL MENTALITY IN THE ACTIVITIES OF WORLD
PEDAGOGICAL SPECIALISTS.

Abstract. This article examines the importance of working on the means of improving the pedagogical skills of students, linking the concepts of “ability” and “pedagogical ability” with the national mentality in the activities of World pedagogical specialists.

Keywords: international organizations, teaching technologies, improving the quality of education and training, cooperation pedagogy, collaborative and cooperative technologies of Education.

РАБОТА НАД СРЕДСТВАМИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО
МАСТЕРСТВА УЧАЩИХСЯ, СВЯЗЫВАЯ ПОНЯТИЯ “ОДАРЕННОСТЬ” И
“ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОДАРЕННОСТЬ” В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ МИРОВЫХ
ПЕДАГОГОВ С НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫМ МЕНТАЛИТЕТОМ.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение работы над средствами повышения педагогического мастерства учащихся в деятельности мировых педагогов, связывающих понятия “одаренность” и “педагогическая одаренность” с национальным менталитетом.

Ключевые слова: международные организации, Технологии обучения, повышение качества образования, педагогика сотрудничества, коллаборативные и кооперативные технологии обучения.

Dunyoda xalqaro tashkilotlar hamda dunyoning aksariyat davlatlari tomonidan ta’lim barqaror taraqqiyotni ta’minlaydigan asosiy kuch sifatida e’tirof etilib, 2030 yilgacha belgilangan yangi ta’lim kontseptsiyasida “o’qitish sifatini baholash jarayoni va vositalarini takomillashtirish, erishilgan natijalarni aniqlash imkonini beruvchi mexanizmlarni amaliyotga joriy etish” dolzarb vazifa etib belgilandi. Ayniqsa, hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida ta’lim-tarbiya sifatini loyihalashtirish, o’quv dialogi asosida ta’lim jarayonini individuallashtirish, hamkorlikda o’qitish texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish va amaliyotga tatbiq etishning metodik tizimini takomillashtirishga alohida e’tibor qaratilmoqda.

Jahonda hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida ta’lim-tarbiya sifatini takomillashtirish bo’yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ilmiy izlanishlarda o’quv-tarbiya jarayoni natijaviyligiga alohida e’tibor

qaratilib, hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida shaxsiy-insonparvarlik yondashuviga asoslangan o'qitish modellarini ishlab chiqish zarurligiga asosiy urg'u berilmoqda. Ayniqsa, hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida ta'lim-tarbiya sifatini takomillashtirishning metodik shart-sharoitlarini aniqlashtirish, hamkorlikda o'qitishning kontseptual g'oyalarini amaliyotga tatbiq etishga oid ilmiy jihatdan asoslangan taklif va tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, ta'limning kollaborativ va kooperativ texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish, oila, maktab integratsiyasini ta'minlashning pedagogik mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Respublikamizda amalga oshirilayotgan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy islohotlar pivojlangan demokratik davlat barpo etish talablariga mos ravishda yoshlarning ta'limi va tarbiyasi sifatini oshirish, o'quv jarayoniga ta'limning zamonaviy shakllari va usullarini joriy etish vazifasini qo'yadi. Mazkur vazifani amalga oshirish shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim strategiyasi talablariga ko'ra, hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida ta'lim-tarbiya sifatini takomillashtirishni taqozo etmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida "Umumiy o'rta ta'lim sifatini tubdan yaxshilash, informatika, matematika, fizika, kimyo, biologiya, ayniqsa, chet tillar kabi boshqa muhim va fundamental fanlarni chuqurlashtirilgan tarzda o'rganish" vazifa etib belgilandi. Natijada hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida ta'lim-tarbiya sifatini takomillashtirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlarini aniqlashtirish, oila va maktab faoliyatini integratsiyalashning pedagogik ta'minotini ishlab chiqish alohida zarurat kasb etishini ko'rsatmoqda.

Ona tili o'qitish metodikasining bosh vazifasi o'quvchilarning o'zbek tili lug'at boyligini to'liq o'zlashtirib olishlarini ta'minlashdir.

Til va nutq tafakkur bilan uzviy bog'lanadi. Fikr nutqda shakllanadi va reallashadi. Tilni egallash va nutq o'stirish bilan o'quvchining fikrlash qobiliyati ham o'sadi.

Bilish nazariyasiga ko'ra analitik-sintetik ishlar yordamida til ustida kuzatishdan umumiy xulosa chiqarishga, nazariy ta'rif va qoidaga, shular asosida, yana og'zaki va yozma tarzidagi nutqiy aloqaga, to'g'ri yozuv va to'g'ri talaffuzga o'tiladi. O'quvchilar jonli nutqiy aloqaga to'g'ri talaffuz va to'g'ri yozuvni elementar nazariy ma'lumotlar asosida amaliy egallash orqali kirishadilar. Ular til materiallarini kuzatish, tahlil qilish orqali elementar nazariy qoidalar chiqaradilar. o'rgangan, o'zlashtirilgan nazariy qoidalarni amaliyotga ongli ravishda tadbiq etadilar.

Pedagogika fani o'quvchilarni har tomonlama rivojlantirish va ularni tarbiyalash masalalarini ilmiy tomondan ishlab beradi. Ona tili o'qitish metodikasi pedagogika fani yangiliklariga, uning yuqorida qayd etilgan masalalarni ilmiy tomondan ishlab bergan ma'lumotlariga asoslanadi.

Ona tili metodikasini umumiy pedagogika bilan bog'lash ayniqsa boshlashg'ich sinflarda muhimdir.

Ona tili o'qitish metodikasi ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish shakllarini va usullarini yuqoridagi maqsadlarni amalga oshirishga yo'naltiriladi.

Til fikrni shakllantirish va bayon qilish, taassurot, his, kechinmalarni ifodalashda muhim o'rin tutadi. Til jamiyat a'zolarining bir-biri bilan o'zaro aloqasi uchun xizmat qiladigan vositadir. Bu vosita qanchalik takomillashsa, fikr shunchalik aniq, ta'sirchan ifodalanadi.

Til muhim tarbiya vositasidir. Badiiy adabiyotlarni, gazeta, jurnallarni o'qigan bola o'zida eng yaxshi hislatlarni tarbiyalab boradi. Muomala madaniyatini egallaydi.

Ona tili boshlangich sinfda asosiy o'rinni egallar ekan, har bir o'quvchida ona tiliga qiziqish va muhabbatni tarbiyalash zarur.

Ona tili metodikasi umumiy pedagogika bilan ham o'zaro bog'lanadi.

Kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarning kollektiv va shaxsiy o'quv faoliyatida zarur bo'lgan ko'p odat va ko'nikmalari hali tarbiyalanmagan bo'ladi. Tashkilotchilik, kollektiv ishga tez kirishish, e'tibor bilan eshitish, o'qish va yozish, aktiv va mustaqil ishlash, barcha ishlarni puxta va saranjom, iloji boricha, chiroyli bajarish kabi ko'nikma va odatlar o'qituvchi va maktab tomonidan amalga oshiriladigan umumpedagogik tadbirlar sistemasini tashkil etadi. Tarbiyaning shunga o'xshash nazariy va amaliy masalalarini pedagogika ishlab beradi. O'qituvchi pedagogik talablarni amalga oshirsagina, ona tilini o'rgatishda o'ziga xos prinsplarni ishlab chiqa oladi.

Ona tili o'qitish metodikasi o'zbek tilini amaliy va ma'lum qismini nazariy egallashni nazarda tutadi, shuning uchun ham lingvistikaga oid tushunchalar (fonetika va fonologiya, leksikologiya va frazeologiya, so'z yasalishi va etimologiya, grammatika – morfologiya va sintaksis, stilistika, shuningdek, orfoepiya, grafika, orfografiya) metodikaning muhim asosi hisoblanadi.

Demak, ona tili o'qitish jarayoniga ta'limning zamonaviy shakllari va usullarini joriy etish orqali Bo'lajak pedagoglarning pedagogik qobiliytlari rivojlantiriladi. Ta'lim-tarbiya sifatini takomillashtirishda ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonlarini tizimli loyihalashtirish va pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash, qayta aloqaning intensivligini ta'minlash, pedagogik tizimning ochiqligi, dinamikligi, statistikligi, o'quvchilarning o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishi, intellektual, hissiy, axloqiy, madaniy, jismoniy imkoniyatlarini faollashtirishga erishish lozim.

Uzoq yillar olib borilgan tadqiqotlar pedagogik qobiliyatlar murakkab va ko'p qirrali psixologik bilimlardan iboratligini ko'rsatib berdi. Ana shu tadqiqot ma'lumotlaridan foydalani, pedagogik qobiliyatlar tuzilishida muhim o'rin egallaydigan qator komponentlar /tarkibiy qismlar/ ni ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin:

Didaktik qobiliyatlar – bu bolalarga o'quv materialini aniq va ravshan tushuntirib, oson qilib yetkazib berish, bolalarda fanga qiziqsh uyg'otib, ularda mustaqil faol fikrlashni uyg'ota biladigan qobiliyatlardir.

Didaktik qobiliyatga ega bo'lgan Talaba zarurat tug'ilganda qiyin o'quv materialini – osonroq, murakkabrog'ini soddaroq, tushunish qiyin bo'lganini tushunarliroq qilib o'quvchilarga moslashtirib bora oladi. Talabaning manna shu xislatlarini bilib olgan o'quvchilar odatda: «Talabaning eng muxim tomoni ham uning hamma narsani aniq-ravshan va tushunarli qilib berishidada. Bunday Talabaning qo'lida maza qilib o'qiging keladi»; «Unisi esa hyech narsaga yaramaydigan Talaba, hyecham aniq tushuntirib bera olmas edi»; «O'quv materialini oldida tirik odamlar emas, balki qandaydir mexanizmlar bordek, zerikarli va noaniq – mujmal qilib tushuntiradi. Biz bunday Bo'lajak pedagoglarni yoqtirmaymiz»-deydilar.

Hozirgi tushunchamizdagi kasbiy maxorat shunchaki bilimlarni osonroq, hammabob va tushunarli qilib o'quvchilar ongiga yetkazib berish qobiliyatigina emas, balki shu bilan birga o'quvchilarning mustaqil ishlarini, ularning bilish faolligini oqilona va moxirlik bilan boshqarib, ularni kerakli, tomonga yo'naltirib turishdan iborat qobiliyatni ham o'z ichiga oladi.

Mana shu qobiliyatlar asosida o'quvchilar psixologiyasiga xos doimiy ustanovka /yo'naltirish/ yetadi. Qobiliyatli pedagog o'quvchilarning tayyorlik darajasini, ularning taraqqiyot darajasini hisobga olgan holda bolalarning nimani bilishi va nimani bilmasligini, nimalarni allaqachon esdan chiqarganliklarini tasavvur qila oladi.

Ko'pchilik Bo'lajak pedagoglarga, ayniqsa xafsalasiz Bo'lajak pedagoglarga, o'quv materiali oddiygina va hych qanday aloxida tushuntirish hamda izoh berishni talab qilmaydigandek tuyuladi.

Bunday Bo'lajak pedagoglar o'quvchilarni emas, balki birinchi galda o'zlarini nazarda tutib ish olib boradilar. Shuning uchun ham o'quv materialini o'ziga qarab tanlaydilar. Qobiliyatli, tajribali Bo'lajak pedagoglar esa o'zlarini o'quvchi o'rniga qo'yib, kattalar uchun aniq-ravshan va tushunarli bo'lgan material o'quvchilar uchun noaniq va tushunarsiz bo'lishi mumkin degan nuqtai nazarda bo'ladila. Materialni bayon etish jarayonida qobiliyatli Talaba turli o'quvchilarning qanday tushunayotganliklari va zarur bo'lganda dars bayonotiga alohida e'tibor berishga intilayotganliklari kabi qator belgilariga qarab to'g'ri tasavvur qilib, xulosa chiqara oladi.

Ana shunday pedagogik qobiliyatni aniqlash uchun psixolog N.F.Gonobolin juda qulay test tavsiya etadi. Bu testga ko'ra bilish xarakteridagi matnda Talabaning fikri buyicha ayrim sinfo'quvchilari uchun qiyin deb hisoblangan qismlarni alohida ko'rsatib, nima uchun bu qismlarning qiyinligini tushuntirib berish, shundan so'ng esa matnni o'quvchilarga yengil va ularning o'zlashtirishlari uchun qulay qilib qayta tuzish tavsiya etiladi.

Qobiliyatli Talaba shu bilan bir qatorda materialni o'zlashtirish, o'quvchilarga biroz nafas olib o'zlariga kelib olishlari va o'z diqqat -e'tiborlarini bir joyga qo'yib, ayrim qo'zg'alishlarni «sundirib» boshqalarini esa jadallashtirib, ularning bushashganligini, sustligini va loqaydliligini yengishlari uchun zamin tayyorlash zarurligini ham nazarda tutadi. Bunday Talaba zarur sharoit yaratilmaguncha darsni boshlamaydi. Haddan tashqari shiddat bilan boshlangan dars o'quvchilarda himoya qiluvchi tormozlanishni vujudga keltirib, miya faoliyati tormozlanadi, Talabaning so'zlari yetarlicha idrok qilinmaydi.

Akademik qobiliyatlar – matematika, fizika, biologiya, ona tili, adabiyot, tarix va boshqa shu kabi fanlarga xos qobiliyatlardir.

Qobiliyatli Talaba o'z fanini faqat kurs hajmidagi emas balki atroflicha keng, chuo'ur bilib, bu soxada erishilgan yutuqlar va kashfiyotlarni doimiy ravishda kuzata borib, o'quv materialini mutlaqo erkin egallab, unga kata qiziqish bilan qaraydi hamda ozgina bo'lsada tadqiqot ishlarini olib boradi.

Ko'pchilik tajribali pedagoglarning aytishlaricha, Talaba o'z Fani buyicha yuksak bilim saviyasiga erishish, boshqalarni qoyil qilib xayratda qoldirish, o'quvchilarda katta qiziqish uyg'ota olish uchun u yuksak madaniyatli, har tomonlama mazmunli, keng erudisiyali /bilimdon/ odam bo'lmog'i lozim.

Bunday Bo'lajak pedagoglar haqida o'quvchilar «Maxmud aka xudi professorning o'ziginasi-ya. Biz uning bilmagan birorta soxasi bormikin deb tez-tez uylab turamiz. Darslarga u butun vujudi bilan kirishib ketadi» deydilar. Ba'zan o'quvchilar o'z Talabasi haqida «Baqir-chaqir qiladi-yu, ammo zarracha bilimi yo'q» deb butunlay teskarisini aytisalar juda alam qiladi.

Perseptiv qobiliyatlar – bu o'quvchining, tarbiyalanuvchining ichki dunyosiga kira bilish, psixologik kuzatuvchanlik, o'quvchi shaxsining vaqtinchalik psixik holatlari bilan bog'liq nozik tomonlarini tushuna bilishdan iborat qobiliyatlardir.

Qobiliyatli Talaba bolalarning har qanday mayda-chuyda xatti-harakatlarida, erkin ifodalanadigan ayrim holatlarida hamda ularning ichki dunyosida yuzaga keladigan o'zgarishlarni sezdirmasdan ilib oladi. Ana shunday hollarda o'quvchilar: «Muhabbat opa kimningdir kayfiyatida o'zgarishlar bo'lsa yoki kimdir dars tayyorlamasdan kelgan bo'lsa ko'ziga qaraboq bilib oladi», «Bizning Talabamiz xech qayoqqa qaramasa ham, hamma narsani ko'rib turadi» deydilar.

Nutq qobiliyati – kishining o'z to'yg'u-xislarini nutq yordamida, shu bilan birga mimika va pantomimika yordamida aniq va ravshan qilib ifodalab berish qobiliyatidir. Bu Talabalik kasbiga muxim qobiliyatlardandir. Chunki Talabadan o'quvchilarga axborot asosan ikkinchi signal tizimi – nutq orqali beriladi. Bunda mazmun jihatdan uning ichki va tashqi xususiyatlari nazarda tutiladi.

Darsda qobiliyatli Talabaning nutqi hamma vaqt o'quvchilarga qaratilgan bo'ladi. Talaba yangi materialni tushuntiradimi, o'quvchining javobini sharhlab beradimi, o'quvchilar javobini, ularning xatti-harakatlari yoki xulq-atvorini ma'qullaydimi yoki tanbeh beradimi, xullas, nima qilishidan qat'iy nazar uning nutqi hamma vaqt o'zining ishonchliligi, jozibadorligi kabi ichki quvvat bilan alohida ajralib turishi lozim. Talaba nutqi, uning talaffuzi aniq-ravshan, oddiy va o'quvchilar uchun tushunarli bo'lishi kerak. Beriladigan axborotlari shunday tuzilishi kerakki, bunda o'quvchilarning fikru-zikri va diqqat-e'tiborini yuqori darajada faollashtiradigan bo'lsin. Buning uchun esa Talaba o'rtaga savol tashlab, asta-sekinlik bilan o'quvchilarni to'g'ri javobga olib keladi, o'quvchilarning diqqat-e'tiborini faollashtiruvchi /«Bunda ayniqsa, ziyrak bo'ling!»/, «Uylang, yana uylab ko'ring!»/ kabi so'z va iboralarni o'z me'yorida ishlatadi.

Talaba nutqi jummalarni, murakkab og'zaki izohlarni, qyin atamalarni va zarurati bo'lmasa, turli ta'riflarni ishlatmasligi lozim. Shu bilan birga Talaba shuni ham hisobga olishi kerakki, Talabaning lunda-lunda bo'lib chiqqan qisqa nutqi ko'p hollarda o'quvchilarga tushinarsiz bo'lib qolar ekan. Talabaning o'z o'rnida ishlatilgan hazil aralash va xayrixohlik bildiruvchi arzimagan kinoyali nutqi o'quvchilarni juda jonlantirib, o'quvchilar tomonidan o'tu yaxshi qabul qilinarkan.

Qobiliyatli Talabaning nutqi jonli, obrazli, aniq-ravshan intonasiyali va ifodali, emosiya boy, dona-dona bo'lib, bunda stilistik va grammatik xatolar mutlaqo bo'lmasligi lozim. Bir xil ohangdagi ezma nutq o'quvchilarni juda tez toliqtirib, ularni zeriktiradi va bexafsala qilib quyadi. Shu bilan birga bunday nutq I.P.Pavlovning fiziologik ta'limotiga ko'ra doimiy ta'sir etuvchan qo'zg'ovchiga aylanib, katta bosh miya yarim sharlar pustida tormozlanish jarayonini yuzaga keltirib, o'quvchini ezma va uyquchan qilib quyadi. Nutq tezligi ko'p jihatdan Talabaning individual psixologik xususiyatga bog'liq. Ayrim Talabalar tez gapirsalar boshqalari sekin gapiradilar. Ammo Talaba o'quvchilarning bilimlarni egallab olishlari uchun eng qulay tezlikdagi nutq-o'rtacha jonli nutq ekanligini edan chiqarmasligi lozim.

Shoshqaloq nutq bilim o'zlashtirishga xalaqit berib, bolalarni tez toliqtiradi, muhofazaqiluvchi tormozlanishni yuzaga keltiradi. O'ta sekin lanjlik va zerikishga olib keladi. Nutqning balandligi – qattiq gapirish ham xudi shu singari xollarga olib keladi. Xaddan tashqari qattiq, keskin, baqirib gapirish o'quvchilarning asabiga tegib, ularni tez toliqtirib, muhofaza qiluvchi tormozlanishni yuzaga keltiradi. Mana shu yerda Sharq mutafakkirlaridan Nasriddin Tusiyning «...Talaba nutqi hyech qachon va hyech qayerda zaharxandali, qo'pol yoki qattiq bo'lishi mumkin emas. Dars paytida Talabaning o'zini tuta olmasligi ishni buzishi mumkin...»

degan nasihatini keltirishimiz juda o'rinli bo'lardi. Talabani bush, sekin ovozi yomon eshitiladi. Nutqi imo-ishoralar, turli keskin harakatlar o'quvchilarni jonlantiradi. Bu tariqa imo-ishora va harakatlar tajribali Talabalarda o'z me'yorida ishlatiladi. Lekin bir xildagi tajribali harakatlarning xaddan tashqari ko'p bo'lishi kishining asabiga tegadi.

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